

International Student Mobility and Retention: Evidence from Discrete Choice Experiments

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Summary

1. We investigate what drives international students' university choices and their staying dynamics in the host country after graduation.
2. We collect choice data using two distinct discrete choice experiments and an information experiment which we analyse using various logit models for robustness.
3. The results reveal that tuition fees are the strongest determinant of university choice, students trade off up to €8,597 for higher university rankings, and easing immigration hurdles increases stay probabilities by 11.62–23.99 percentage points.
4. The data shows preference heterogeneity is substantial: visa-requiring students show a 9-point higher stay intention, and students with their own income source show a 4.6–6.2-point increase.
5. In line with prior research, we find that increasing tuition fees will put a halt to the attraction of international talent whereas keeping immigration barriers high and employment opportunities low will force them to test their luck elsewhere.

1. Introduction and Policy Motivation

International student mobility brings substantial economic benefits to host countries, including tuition fees, living expenses and future income tax revenues (OECD, 2017; De Witte and Soncin, 2021). Beyond economic impact, internationalization of higher education may ameliorate cultural enrichment (Halterbeck and Conlon, 2021), enhance quality of education (Diaz Lema and Shaikh, 2026; Haelermans et al., 2026), improve language skills of domestic students (Münch and Hoch, 2013) and fostering social- and trade networks (Bolhaar et al., 2019; Halterbeck and Conlon, 2021). Nevertheless, internationalization in higher education is increasingly under pressure in many Western countries, as governments reconsider policies on funding, migration, and tuition fees. It is insufficiently understood how such policies affect higher education demand from international students. Additionally, quantitative evidence about staying dynamics of graduates is non-existent. The present study aims to fill these gaps to ameliorate evidence-based policy making in Flanders and

Europe. We focus on the following two research questions: (1) What factors do international students value when choosing a university?; (2) What factors influence international graduates' decision to stay in the host country?

In Peeters and De Witte (2026), we study the dynamics of international student mobility and graduate retention at a large, multi-campus European university. We conduct two discrete choice experiments and an information experiment among students from all faculties, and collect background information to test for heterogeneous effects. Analysing the obtained choice data using various logistic regression models, we unravel preference structures of international students in tertiary education..

2. Data and Methodology

We use two discrete choice experiments, a policy-oriented methodology rooted in microeconomic theory of preferences. We set up two separate experiments, labelled “decks”, for each research question. Deck 1 analyses the preference structures of the choice of university, whereas Deck 2 analyses the factors influencing the decision whether to stay or not upon graduation. In our discrete choice experiment - a survey-based method - respondents iteratively choose between two hypothetical alternatives, which are defined by five attributes. For each attribute we define several associated levels, which we subsequently combine efficiently into hypothetical alternatives. Per deck, the respondent receives six choice sets.

The survey was administered early 2025 and yielded 748 observations. We use a conditional logit model, rooted in Random Utility Theory, as our baseline model to estimate the utility or relative importance associated with each attribute-level combination in both decks.

To account for limitations of both the discrete choice experiment and the conditional logit model, we include several robustness checks to our analysis. The results show that our baseline findings are generally robust.

3. Results

Five key results emerge from the analysis:

First, tuition fees and university reputation appear crucial in attracting international talent. Among the five attributes included, disutility from higher fees is the highest. This result suggests that rising tuition fees may put downward pressure on demand for university services among international students. We also find substantial willingness to pay for universities with a high ranking, as a proxy for quality. We find that international students are willing to forego up to €8,597 in annual tuition fees to attend a higher ranked university.

Second, gross salary is the most influential to keep international talent, closely followed by the ease of getting a residence permit and quality of life. Key to keep self-educated internationals here is to keep immigration barriers - the process of receiving a residence permit - low and swift, a finding echoed by OECD (2025). A high quality of life appears as an equally important condition for retention of international talent. Our respondents display a willingness to sacrifice between €288-€761 and €360-€754 in gross salary (resp.) to attain better situations in both attributes.

Third, relevant job opportunities are key to retain international talent. Our evidence shows international students value the number of relevant job opportunities only mildly. The valuation is somewhat higher for Master's students and students from outside the EEA. But we also monitor that students who are closer to the labour market have a substantially higher stay intention.

Fourth, several student characteristics influence their stay intention. We find that students from outside the EEA have a nine percentage points higher stay intention. A similar picture emerges for students from poorer countries (measured by GDP per capita), where we find a near two percentage points increase for each \$10,000 less GDP per capita in the home country. Additionally, we find that Master students have an 8.85 to 10.18 percentage points higher stay intention. For students with an income source, this figure becomes 4.54 to 9.24.

Fifth, substantial preference heterogeneity is present among international students. First, non-EEA students put stronger emphasis on job opportunities and low immigration barriers, reflecting the deep commitment they make by studying abroad. Second, Master degree students also put more focus on job prospects, as they are closer to the labour market. Third, students with a part-time employment or student job encounter greater disutility from higher tuition fees and value social integration relatively more, reflecting their tendencies to integrate in society. Fourth, we find substantial heterogeneity in preferences for tuition fees: one group exhibits a strong disutility from higher fees, while the other is largely indifferent. This suggests that targeted financial aid may enhance inclusivity among international students.

4. Policy Recommendations

The findings of the present paper offer several insights for policy makers at the regional, national and supranational level.

1. Higher tuition fees, following for instance from reductions in funding for international students, create higher disutility's. This will put downward pressure on applications, making international talent alter their direction to other countries. Staying competitive in the attraction of international talent should be paired with the necessary funding. Critically, this funding must be regarded as investment, as retention of international students generate substantial economic benefits on the middle- and long-term (De Witte and Soncin, 2021). Additionally, heterogeneity in tuition fee preferences suggests that targeted scholarship and financial support policies can improve access to higher education for international students.
2. To attract the international talent of tomorrow, it is imperative to keep strong focus on international university rankings as a signal of institutional quality. To keep up such rankings, there should be focus on high teaching standards with improved student-to-staff ratios, strong research output with proven track records and building bridges with the labour market.
3. Countries should lower immigration barriers for self-educated international talent that wants to stay and work in the host country. Measures taken such as the Belgian orientation year are a good starting point. Additionally, procedures should be streamlined and made easier. We

estimate that fast-track visa processing for skilled non-EEA graduates may yield €27.7 to €83.0 million annually to the Flemish economy.

4. International students in our study place only modest weight on the number of available job opportunities. However, earlier research shows that poor job prospects are the main reason they leave after graduation. This gap suggests a need to better inform students about factors that support successful job entry, including social integration and language skills. Our estimates indicate that improving labour market conditions for international graduates could generate between €40.0 and €172.7 million in added value to the Flemish economy.

What is BRIDGE?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

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